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Hybrid algorithm based on Genetic Algorithm and Tabu Search for Reconfiguration Problem in Smart Grid Networks Using “R”

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Abstract

Reconfiguration of distribution networks aims to support the decision support, planning and/or real-time control of the operation of the electricity network. It is accomplished modifying the network structure of distribution feeders by changing the sectionalizing switches. Ensure higher levels of continuity and reliability to the electricity supply service are some of the requirements of consumers and electric power providers in the Smart Grid (SG) context. The goal of this paper is to propose a hybrid algorithm (Genetic and Tabu) for the reconfiguration problem based on “R” in order to better support the decision making process. Beyond that, “R” modeling of electricity networks improves the response time when handling issues of network reconfiguration using graph theory. The status of switches is decided according to graph theory subject to the radiality constraint of the distribution networks. The algorithm is presented and simulation results of IEEE 16-bus system, showing good results and computational efficiency.

Keywords: Smart Grid, Hybrid Algorithm, Network Reconfiguration, “R” modeling

1 Introduction

Electricity has become an essential consumer goods to society. A fault or short circuit at a certain point in the network makes a protective device operates, leaving whole load (consumers) connected from that point without electricity supply. The need to initiate a process of reconfiguring a network of electricity has at least three capital motives [1]: (i) performing maintenance on the components of the electric grid; (ii) an imbalance of electric power; and (iii) power failure.

In general, the problem of reconfiguration of power networks aims to seek an optimal operation strategy with the intention of minimize losses and provide an appropriate balancing of the loads in the system, taking into account the protection and quality of electricity supply to consumers. It is a multi-objective, combinatorial, nonlinear constrained optimization problem [24]. This is because there are multiple constraints, which must not be violated while finding an optimal or near-optimal solution to the distribution network reconfiguration problem.

The problem consists in finding, among all possible combinations, a set of configurations which (i) minimize the number of switching operations while keeping the radial structure of the system, (ii) reduce the energy loss and (iii) reducing the amount of consumers without electricity supply, in order

to safeguarding restrictions voltage levels at the point of load, maximum current flow in the branches, the lines flow capacity and nominal power of the transformers.

The heuristic methods focus on finding an approximate solution when classic methods fail to find any exact solution. In the reconfiguration problem context involve development of rules to minimize the number of switching operations.

A genetic algorithm (GA) is a method for search and optimization that imitates the processes of evolution and natural selection [2]. GA is computational model which simulate the procedure of biologic evolve. Due to their ability to find global optimal solutions for solving large-scale combinatorial optimization problems, GA is applied widely because it has the character of independent of grad in whole search and optimization, including the supply restoration problem [3].

Tabu Search is a general technique proposed by [4] for obtaining approximate solutions to combinatorial optimization problems. Tabu Search consists basically of generating a number of appropriate possible configurations and choosing those that present desired characteristics as far as the objective to be attained is concerned. During the Tabu Search, in order to prevent from the repeated search of the local optimal solution and reach the global optimal solution of the problem, some historical information related to the evolution of the search should be kept and such information will be used to guide the movement from one solution to the next one avoiding visiting repeated solutions. Taboo list is used to store the local optimal solutions that have been searched recently.

Tabu Search is a technique that consists basically of generating a number of appropriate possible configurations and choosing those that present desired characteristics as far as the objective to be attained is concerned.

This paper proposes a solution to this problem using a hybrid algorithm (approach) and the modeling of a reconfiguration problem based on “R” in the Smart Grid context presented in this paper aims to propose a flexible modeling for protection solutions, optimization, and dynamic generation.

The proposed approach explores two existing popular methodologies to mitigate the problem (Genetic Algorithm and Tabu Search) to deals with disorders of a power system in regard to interruption of supply of electric power and other anomalies. The algorithm is presented and simulation results of IEEE 16-bus system, showing good results and computational efficiency.

2 Related Work

In recent years, considerable research has been conducted for loss minimization in the area of network reconfiguration of distribution systems.

The objective of the reconfiguration is alter the topology of the network and obtain the best possible configuration minimizing the distribution losses with changing the sectionalizing switches. The reconfiguration problem has the following constrains [5]: (i) Power flow equations; (ii) Upper and lower bounds of nodal voltages; (iii) Upper and lower bounds of line currents and, (iv) Feasible conditions in terms of network topology (radial structure).

The reconfiguration of power system is difficult to deal due to its combinatorial nature [6]. The difficulty in mathematical formulation to fulfill the constraints (of the problem) used to model the behavior of system elements, with appropriate computational time for decision making in real-time, are not taken into account the most recent research [7][8][9] in relation to a solution of reconfiguration in real-time.

A large number of papers has been published so for on Tabu Search algorithm for various combinatorial optimization solution [10]. The Tabu Search method used in [11] is a popular solution technique in combinatorial optimization problem.

In [12] presented the application of Tabu Search as meta-heuristic method for network reconfiguration problem in radial distribution system. Several approaches to the reconfiguration problem have been proposed. In [13] and [14] use mixed integer linear programming, and [15] use Tabu Search.

A new method for the restoration of service is presented in [16] which uses a multi-objective version of the Tabu Search metaheuristic. Two criteria are considered: the minimization of not restored load and the number of switching operations involved.

A method of distribution system reconfiguration for loss reduction using a simple GA is proposed in [17]. Strings which represented switch status, a fitness function consisting of total system losses, and penalty values of voltage drop limit and current capacity limit.

In [18] is presented a method based on GA for Loss Minimization in Distribution Systems using a vertex encoding/decoding to determine the network configuration. The vertex based number was used in GAS for encoding/decoding the chromosomes (strings). The Prufer number ensured that the system structure will be radial for the distribution system.

A real application was proposed by [19]. It proposes and evaluates a method that improves the adaptability and efficiency of genetic algorithms when applied to the minimal loss reconfiguration problem.

The graph theory together with the laws of the Kirchoff's loop (or mesh) and the theory of circuits [21], have been used to support the representation of diverse applications, simulations and analysis of power networks. An abstract model, in graph form, of a power network was proposed by [20], which a node (vertex) representing a bus and an edge represents a transmission line connecting two buses.

In [22], a graph theory is used, particularly a directed graph to represent a power networks in order to determine the contributions of specific generators in terms of power flows at different loads. Each vertex is considered a root generator and the edges represent transmission lines, from which it generates all possible subgraphs oriented.

Another use of graph theory is found in [23], in which the problem to estimate the location of faulty components (Fault Section Estimation - FSC) is transformed into a problem of partitioning the graph vertices leading into account the priorities of these to spawn new subsets of graphs connected and balance leading into account the priorities of these to spawn new subsets of graphs connected and balanced.

The graph theory was used by [24] to represent the entire electrical system based on the configuration states of circuit breakers that connect the components of the power network. It was proposed a method for reconfiguration and restoration of electricity supply in contingency situations using genetic algorithms. In the genetic algorithm, the representation of a chromosome was used to represent the configuration of a set of circuit breakers belonging to the electrical system.

Figure 1: Mindmap of major approaches in reconfiguration problem

The use of AI based methods has proven them to be valuable in a wide variety of applications, the caution is that they do not represent the best solution in some implementations. Figure 1 shows majors approaches in reconfiguration problems. Hybrid algorithms based methods offer the potential of significant reductions in solution times [25].

In [25] presented a useful paper that explores existing popular methodologies to mitigate the re-configuration problem.

3 Issues and Motivations

Smart Grids (SG) are a required solution for electricity systems in which, in resume, some integration and intelligence is deployed at the electricity systems in order to support a better overall operation. Some issues and motivations are listed below:

- Common problem for electrical engineers in the area
- Would benefit from a flexible and resourceful computational approach that could both represent and provide a robust framework for computation
- Would require a framework in order to assist the reconfiguration decision process and issues (real time computation, inherent complexity, parameters representation and scalability, other)

The modeling of a reconfiguration problem based on R in the Smart Grid context aims to deal and assist in the decision making in regard to performance towards reconfiguration problems of the power grid. Possible reconfiguration scenarios are listed below:

1. Situation: Optimization in supply of electric power: network reconfiguration and load balancing.
 - Strategy: Identify points of attention (warnings of possible overloads - threatened thresholds);
 - Action: Propose improvement in the quality of service of electricity supply proposing a more optimized configuration of alternative network, while respecting the constraints of voltage levels, ability to flow lines and nominal power of the transformers.
2. Situation: Distributed Generation (DG) - Network reconfiguration and load balancing.
 - Strategy: Check the demand and / or load variation and identify the distributed energy sources connected to the power network as well as their respective loads available;
 - Action: Propose an optimum and balanced topology network with the inclusion of distributed generation sources.

4 Modeling with “R”

Computer modeling helps in proposing solutions to scientific problems using simulation. To this end, we analyzed the phenomena, develop mathematical models to describing the problem, and prepare computer codes to support the solutions.

“R” [29] is a free software environment for statistical computing and graphics. The selection of it was influenced by the motive that “R” is not just a statistics package, it is a language and could be apply an emerging, free and open source technology to the study of power systems engineering for Internet-based utilization, for economic benefits to students of developing among others implementations interests.

The computational model presented aims to propose a “R” based modeling of protection solutions, optimization, and dynamic generation that deals with disorders of a power system in relation to interruption of electric power supply and other anomalies.

The “R” computing environment could also be freely used for mathematical and engineering computations that are not dependent on the project in question. R has good provision for complex number operations, vector and matrix manipulation, algebra and ODEs (ordinary differential equation), and visualization packages.

“R” is a language and environment for statistical computing that provides a wide variety of statistical (linear and nonlinear modeling, classical statistical tests, time series analysis, classification, clustering, among others) and graphical techniques, and is highly extensible.

Igraph [30] is a free software package for creating and manipulating undirected and directed graphs. It includes implementations for classic graph theory problems like minimum spanning trees and network flow, and also implements algorithms for some recent methods for analyzing network such as the pursuit of community structure.

Scripts of power flow computer simulations (Gauss-Siedel & Newton-Raphson techniques) have been implemented by RPowerLabs [31] using “R” and have been engaged as a module in our algorithm.

The distribution system has a configuration that includes a set of circuits represented by types of switches: tie switch and sectionalizing switch that are energized, forming a tree from the point of view of graph theory. The circuits that are not energized are called branches of connection (disconnected

Figure 2: (a) Mapping computational model of the power grid and a (b) three-dimensional matrix of data

graph), and a suitable replacement (a connection from a reconfiguration) of a branch connection with a branch of the tree creates a new tree (a power system reconfigured) represented by a new connected graph (in which there is always a path consisting of branches between any two nodes).

Given a connect graph $G = (V, E)$ and ($degree(v_i) \geq 1$) without loops ($e_i = (v_i, v_i) \notin G$) which V corresponds to the set of vertices, $V = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n\}$, and E corresponds to the set of edges, $E = \{e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n\}$, this may represent an infrastructure reconfiguration of power networks, as shown in Figure 2a, the branches between nodes 7-16 (e_8), 10-14 (e_{13}), 5-11 (e_7) are the tie switches which are open and the remaining continuous switches are called sectionalizing switches which are generally closed, as follows:

- The set of vertices V represents the generator supplying (Feeders) and the intersections of the transmission lines (Load Center).
- The set of edges E represents the switches (sectionalizing switches and tie switches) and transmission line. Each edges e_i may contain a set of attributes (such as resistance, reactance, among others) or devices (such as circuit breakers and distributed generators) beyond the transmission line properties. The representation of these data is accomplished through a three-dimensional matrix $M = (d \times p \times e)$ Figure 2b, in which:
 - The line (d) represents the attributes or devices;
 - The column (p) stores the values of attributes or properties of the devices and the segment of the transmission line between the device and its predecessor.
 - Dimension (e) of the matrix (M) stores the attributes and/or devices (d) and its properties (p).

A subgraph of a graph G is a graph whose vertex set is a subset of that of G , and whose adjacency relation is a subset of that of G restricted to this subset. In this mapping, subgraphs are constructed in such a way that the power can reach to all vertices in that subgraphs.

5 The Hybrid Algorithm and Simulation Scenario

In this section, we present a hybrid algorithm based on genetic and Tabu Search algorithms, as shown in Figure 3, for the network reconfiguration focused on infrastructure analysis based on “R” in order to better support the decision making process.

The validation of the flexible modeling will be presented (which uses graph theory), simple and applied on the IEEE 16-bus test system (Figure 2a) using a proposed hybrid algorithm developed in the simulation environment named “R” [29] and Igraph package.

1. Read Topology and Data
2. Generate initial solution (S0)
3. Be P_a the active loss of S0
4. $Min \leftarrow P_a$
5. Be K_o the Tie Switches on S0;
6. For each K_o
 - 6.1. Close switch;
 - 6.2. Search loop;
 - 6.3. Store loops in $List_c$ (list of loops possibilities);
7. End-For
8. For each loop in $List_c$
 - 8.1. Choose switches based on selection process
 - 8.2. Store chosen switches in $List_{ps}$ (list of switches chosen by elitism)
9. End-For
10. Create TL (Tabu List)
11. For each topologies generated by switches status in $List_{ps}$
 - 11.1. If not exist in TL
 - 11.1.1. Update in TL
 - 11.1.2. Compute P_a
 - 11.1.3. If ($P_a < Min$)
 - 11.1.3.1. $Min \leftarrow P_a$
 - 11.2. End-If
12. End-For
13. End

Figure 3: A Pseudo code of the proposed hybrid algorithm

Lets explain, in a brief way, how the proposed hybrid algorithm works. Using an initial topology (Figure 2a), the hybrid algorithm figure out new topologies by closing opened switches and searching for loops. To this, it will manipulate the edge status which could be opened and closed, for example, in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Change the topology by change the status of the tie switch (e_7)

When closing a previously opened switch (tie switch) the branch (edge) between nodes 5-11 (e_7), the radially propriety of the system is violated, generating loops, as shows in Figures 5, 6 and 7.

Based on the elitism selection method of the genetic algorithm (in line 8.1 of the Figure 3, the best individuals (switches) of each loop are used in the creation of a new population (system topology according to new switches status - open/close), and the result is chosen as possibility of a solution ($List_{ps}$).

From all records store in $List_{ps}$ that was generated by changing the status of switches and does not belongs to a Taboo List (TL in line 11.1 of the Figure 3) calculate and update Tabu List, just to

Figure 5: Loop 1 (Feeders 1-2), generated by closing switch 7 (e_7) between nodes 5-11

Figure 6: Loop 2 (Feeders 1-2), generated by closing switch 8 (e_8) between nodes 7-16

Figure 7: Loop 3 (Feeders 1-2), generated by closing switch 13 (e_{13}) between nodes 10-14

avoiding compute repeated solutions. Taboo list is used to store the local optimal solutions that have been searched (calculate) recently.

After the development of the proposed algorithm according to the computational modeling on graph theory using “R” approach, we obtained an equivalent results as shown in Table 1.

Simulations	Final Loss (KW)	Reduction (%)	Topology (Tie Switches)
Hybrid Algorithm	466,13	8.86	$e_8 - e_9 - e_{11}$
ACS-R [32]	466,13	8.86	$e_8 - e_9 - e_{11}$
Civanlar [33]	483,88	5,38	$e_7 - e_8 - e_{11}$
Guimaraes [34]	466,13	8.86	$e_8 - e_9 - e_{11}$
Gomes [35]	466,13	8.86	$e_8 - e_9 - e_{11}$
Lorenzetti [36]	466,13	8.86	$e_8 - e_9 - e_{11}$
Mantovani [37]	466,13	8.86	$e_8 - e_9 - e_{11}$

Table 1: Results obtained from IEEE 16-bus test system

It is verified that only [33] does not find the optimal topology (based on opened switches - tie switches). The proposed hybrid algorithm, together with the other algorithms, figure out a optimum topology with lower losses of active power. The topology found is illustrated in Figure 8

The model is flexible enough in such a way that, with this information (Table 1) it is possible to propose a network reconfiguration, for instance, to make the system optimized, thus minimizing

Figure 8: Optimal topology found - tie switches e_8 , e_9 , e_{11}

dependence on a single transformer, thereby improving the quality of power supply or even reducing the consequences of a possible failure.

6 Final Considerations

The proposed hybrid algorithm and computational modeling for the reconfiguration problem based on “R” in order to better support the decision making process based on “R” in the Smart Grid context has been discussed and illustrated. The proposed hybrid algorithm uses aspects of Tabu Search, Genetic algorithms and graph theory based on “R” modeling language and effectively produces a easy way to model the system that may deal with disorders of a power system in regard to interruption of supply of electric power and other anomalies.

The basic new advantages brought by using “R” and the proposed modeling method (SG features and capabilities mapping) is that, firstly, we get a more straightforward way to represent the components of a reconfiguration Smart Grid problem and, secondly, “R” modeling creates a new set of possibilities in terms of “handling and/or manipulating” the problem being considered. This is basically due to the inherent capabilities resulting from using graph theory to handle a multi-objective problem such as the reconfiguration or optimization ones in the Smart Grid context.

The “R” model proposed is adaptable to the context of network reconguration and can be expanded even beyond the scenario presented. For future work, it is expected to adapt the model to simulate (i) an autonomic decision making to the system using priority in terms of loads (that could be a hospital, industries, streets, neighborhoods, cities, among other) before a transformer fails or the insertion of distributed energy resources; (ii) propose, in real time, a network reconguration system aiming to balance the loads (optimization problem) and the minimization of possible occurrences of failures due to overload; (iii) simulate others IEEE topologies test case and analysis the length of time required to perform a computational process (computational time) to find the optimal results (topologies).

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